

Covid-19 outbreak exposes India's chronic healthcare underinvestment

Abhineet Anand¹, Naresh Kumar Tiwari², Ankit Khare³, M.Arvindhan⁴, Prashant Johri⁵

1,2,-Chitkara University Institute of Engineering and Technology, Chitkara University, Punjab

3-School of computer science,University of petroleum & energy studies, Dehradun,

4,5-Galgotias University, Greater Noida, UP

Corresponding Author – abhineet.anand@chitkara.edu.in

Abstract:

The country's infrastructure needed to be reassessed, with an emphasis on improving rural health infrastructure through government facilities and nursing homes, as well as increased manpower, while increasing district-level capabilities. The covid-19 epidemic uncovered a systemic flaw and highlighted our investment in public health infrastructure as a whole. Equipment, medicine, and vaccine supplies are all in short supply, as is a skilled crew, an unmanageable caseload, clean restrooms, and the total health facility. Fitch Solutions warned that despite extra financing, the ongoing paucity of medical investment and health infrastructure would pose hurdles in terms of establishing an effective response to the COVID-19 epidemic in India.

The research further states that the government's desire for universal health care coverage will boost growth in India's pharmaceutical and health care markets. The improvement of business environments and anticipated health care changes will benefit innovative medication producers and such a market will continue to exhibit enormous potential as the third-largest pharmacy market in the Asia-Pacific region. The fact is that the general medical setting of public hospitals is more separated. If public hospitals are to be responsive to people's health needs, then these institutions' problems should not be situated alone in their inner workings, but under broader conditions (we can call them structural issues) that influence their operation.

Keywords: Covid-19, Telemedicine, Healthcare, Health Scenario.

Introduction

The sickness of coronavirus (COVID-19) has spread over the globe since its outbreak in December 2019. Over three months, it caused more than 5 million illnesses and tens of thousands of deaths. The local medical capacities of vast numbers of people who hurried to hospitals for treatment were rapidly diminished in cities badly impressed by COVID-19, such as Bombay & New Delhi (India), Chinese Wuhan, Italy and New York City (USA)[1]. Many physicians were infected and supplies of medical care were severely depleted. Many governments have called for infected persons with mild symptoms to remain at home and self-quarantined to prevent the collapse of the global health system. The condition of certain home-quarantined individuals, however, has been observed as serious or critical as the disease develops. The prompt treatment and hospitalisation of these patients may result in their death via domestic quarantine[2], [3].

Fitch Solutions warned that despite extra financing, the ongoing paucity of medical investment and health infrastructure would pose hurdles in terms of establishing effective response to the COVID-19

epidemic in India. Fitch Solutions' Country Risk and Industry Research (a unit of Fitch Group) stated in its forecast on the Indian drugs markets that "the continuing lack of medical funding and health infrastructure is telling us how much of the potential epidemic in India would become worse if it is not properly contained." With 8.5 hospital beds, 10,000 people and 8 doctors per 10,000 people, the national health service is not geared towards a crisis[4][5]. In addition, the severe inefficiency, dysfunction and acute shortages in public sector health systems do not meet the increasing population demand. Moreover, over 80% of the population still have no substantial coverage of health insurance and about 68% of Indians do not have access to basic medicines[6]–[8].

The grading agency also mentioned a survey by the Public Health Foundation of India that over the previous two decades free medicines have fallen in public healthcare institutions from 31.2% to 8.9% and from 17.8% to 5.9% for outpatient treatment. The research further states that the government's desire for universal health care coverage will boost growth in India's pharmaceutical and health care markets[1].

The improvement of business environments and anticipated health care changes will benefit innovative medication producers and such a market will continue to exhibit enormous potential as the third-largest pharmacy market in the Asia-Pacific region[9].

The fact is that the general medical setting of public hospitals is more separated. If public hospitals are to be responsive to people's health needs, then these institutions' problems should not be situated alone in their inner workings, but under broader conditions (we can call them structural issues) that influence their operation. It also means that solutions to these problems should not be dictated by narrow management approaches or technocentric methods but should be socially based[10].

Public healthcare will continue for a long time to reach broad parts of under-served populations in emerging countries such as India in terms of health care[11]. This review sets itself the following aims as part of the implementation of the 12th Five-Year Plan Paper as an ambitious programme aimed at achieving "universal health care" in the country:

- i) clarify and demonstrate their enormity in the more significant difficulties facing Indian public hospitals;
- (ii) conditions the circumstances that contribute to the creation of socioeconomic and political sources;
- (iii) provide solutions within the current political and economic systems, in line with the above analysis.

A public hospital for this study must include the most remote PHCs (primary health) at a hospital for tertiary care in a large city. Although their specific duties differ, they are a continuum of precautionary and curative care. While the lower levels should deliver more preventive and curative care for most typical conditions, higher institutions should care for a more chosen range of patients who demand more specialised services, not in the lower public health facility. Moreover, supervisors, training and technical help are in the hands of the supervisor for the smooth functioning of primary facilities. A synthesis of many levels of the public hospitals and a partition at all levels therefore has consequences for all levels[9][12].

Healthcare Scenario in India-Survey

India has one of the lowest public health spending budgets in the world. The country's public healthcare system, which includes both state and federal governments, accounts for about 1.3 percent of GDP, compared to 7.6 percent for OECD countries and 3.6 percent for other BRICS countries[13].

Despite the fact that overall per capita government healthcare spending has nearly doubled from Rs 1,008 in FY15 to Rs 1,944 in FY20, a 15 percent CAGR, it is still deemed poor[14].

Some of the facts about healthcare budget in India

The budget for 2021 boosted healthcare expenditures by 137 percent. Increased healthcare spending under the PM Atmanirbhar Swasth Bharat Yojana will strengthen infrastructure and is in line with industry forecasts of 2.5 percent to 3% of GDP by 2025, as well as the GDP National Health Policy 2017 objective of 2.5 percent by 2025. In India, healthcare will cost Rs 2.23 lakh crore. As part of the Rs 2.23 lakh billion budget, Rs 35,000 crore would be spent on Covid-19 vaccinations. The finance minister also hinted at the arrival of two new vaccinations in the near future. Alongside the National Health Mission, the Pradhan Mantri Atmanirbhar Swasth Bharat Yojana, with a budget of INR 64,180 crore, would be implemented. The new strategy will enhance primary, secondary, and tertiary healthcare systems, reinforce national institutions, and establish new institutions for new and emerging diseases during the next six years[15],[14], [16]. The pledge to expand healthcare spending beyond Covid vaccine costs while avoiding any new taxes or fees to support the vaccination effort is tremendously favourable for public health and the economy. In the long run, this will enhance access to better healthcare facilities. Around 17,000 rural and 11,000 urban health and wellness centres will be built to improve the primary healthcare system. Apart from 3,382 block public health units in 11 states, integrated public health laboratories will be established in districts. There has also been talk about establishing bio-safety laboratories and mobile hospitals in the area. Furthermore, boosting PLI allocation will encourage more capital investment in the pharmaceutical sector, which is in keeping with the Atmanirbhar Bharat push to make India self-sufficient[17].

It was projected that the GST on active pharmaceutical ingredients (API) will be reduced from 18 percent to 12 percent, reversing the inverted duty structure. It had to be one of the flops. The cost of healthcare services for citizens would have been decreased if the import tariff on medical gadgets had been cut. However, no announcement was made about it[10]. This budget might have provided much-needed relief to individuals by granting refunds on medical insurance premiums, as well as boosting pharmaceutical businesses by incentivizing R&D spending. However, there were no safeguards in place this time[10],[2], [5].

Year	Expenditure on Health(In Crs.)	Population(In Crs.)	GDP	Public Expenditure on Health Percentage of GDP
2009-10	72536	117	6477827	3.485
2010-11	83101	118	7784115	3.272
2011-12	96221	120	8736039	3.246
2012-13	108236	122	9951344	3.329
2013-14	112270	123	11272764	3.749
2014-15	121600.23	125	12433749	3.62
2015-16	140054.55	126	13764037	3.596
2016-17	178875.63	128	15253714	3.511
2017-18	213719.58	129	16751688	3.535

Telemedicine System for Covid Patients Monitoring

Telemedicine technology is one of the issues that must be addressed in any conversation. Telemedicine technology needs are as basic or complex as the doctor or organisation[15], [18]. A telemedicine setup requires some fundamental requirements and certain choices. You need

- i) Safe internet access (broadband)
- ii) video platform
- iii) assistance for technology.

You then opt to capture your interaction (registration device) and to support the visit by choosing your peripherals[19]. The following is a fundamental explanation of the conditions needed to begin telemedicine in allergy and immunology.

1. A secure broadband internet connection is the most basic technique in telemedicine. The volume and speed of the internet connection is determined by video quality and the quantity and the speed of data transfer. A base broadband business connection of 50-100 Mbps (megabits/sec) should be adequate.
2. The video connection and the video interface platform are the next crucial piece in a telemedicine system. Various video systems are available and the sort of system you choose relies on the sort of system you decide to use. The fundamental concept is a direct-to-consumer approach in which patients can contact their doctors by using a home computer or

app-enabled smartphone. Usually, these systems are supplied by a third party seller. The second approach is to link two secure places or PCs. In this latter arrangement, the physician controls both ends of the interface and is able to speak with the patients using an already established computer[19]. It is a more expensive solution and requires the patient to go to the remote computer site, usually to a remote health clinic.

3. The support needed for running a programme is also crucial to hardware selection in a telemedicine programme. For any application to work successfully, qualified computer and technical support are vital. Depending on the resources, help might be virtual or personal, but access to the doctor is always crucial. Stable, secure internet access may be ensured by support employees. They must, most crucially, be ready to help with difficulties of technology and hardware that can emerge during a day of the clinic to prevent patient care interruptions[20].
4. If necessary, a recording device is part of the video conferencing set-up. There may be a need for us to record and save parts or all of the interaction, depending upon the state standards in which you practise. Some video and pre-packaged telemedicine solutions allow video to be recorded and archived. If this does not form part of your system, then secure data storage is required (video or written visit documentation based on your local requirements). In some circumstances, based on the EMR manufacturer, this is integrated with an EMR[21].
5. Depending upon what you want to do during your visit and with your telemedicine programme, peripherals and video assistance equipment are necessary. These gadgets are not required to run a programme and can be added later on by a suitable system. Many of them are now connected to USB and connect simply with an existing system. Examples of peripherals include HEENT video otoscopes, electronic stethoscopes to provide cardiovascular assessment and high definition video cameras to display rash or skin lesions (derma scope). One alternative is to add the necessary hardware to the telemedicine cart. This mobile or rolling device is a single unit. The computer should have access, video equipment, electricity (a battery that enables mobility) and storage peripherals. Telemedicine services can be moved into a clinic by a mobile unit so that patients can be used in multiple areas. There are large variations in proposed investments in equipment and capacity[22], [23].

In the last 10 years, a healthcare system has become viable due to recent breakthroughs in wireless and network technologies, linked to current nanotechnological breakthroughs and all-embracing computing systems. Telemedicine is the word used in telecommunications technology for medical diagnosis, treatment and care for patients. Telemedicine focuses on providing understaffed rural places with advanced technology and wireless connectivity as a means of professional health[20]. Telemedicine is one of the advantages of reducing costs because information is cheaper than humans. Advances in medical technology have led to an increase in the number of aged in many countries, and the necessity for home health monitoring expands so patients can live on their own. In addition, the results are increasing. Many physiological signals in their lives can be recorded during day-to-day activities by individuals and potentially used in the early phase to monitor health abnormalities or to automatically warn paramedics in an emergency. In

particular, all research developed and currently employed in this field, for the remote monitoring of physiologic parameters can be grouped into various aspects: sensor type, communication type of data, monitoring device, processing of signals and medical algorithms. These aspects are therefore covered in this section together with current investigations. As illustrated in Figure 1. The main components of the telemedicine system have been the biosignal sensors, processing units, data communications networks and a medical services centre[18].

The biosignal sensors are responsible for the acquisition and transmission of physiological data (patient vital signs). Some research only focuses on small sensors, retaining the mobility of patients and using low operational power for longer battery life to reduce battery volume. The usage of personal area networks or the body network to connect wearable medical sensors might be collected and possibly be integrated into the user garments. In the next phase, the communication layer is often connected with the processing device of every remote monitoring system, where the acquisition, processing, and analysis data and formatting data is transmitted. The treatment unit can evaluate the patient status and trend in the medical condition. Numerous medical algorithms have been created in recent telemedicine to support patient diagnosis and early cardiovascular disease detection. A PC, cell phone or embedded system can be the processing unit (microcontroller, DSP processor and FPGA). Pulse evaluation has been a field of research of interest in the field of physiology among human vital signs for a very long time because it represents an individual's health[24], [25]. Many studies have presented monitoring systems capable of measuring different bio mark signals, QRS detection and classification of arrhythmia, real-time ECG classification algorithms and assessment of cardiac a wireless telemedicine system that provides an effective way to provide patients with health care. Telemedicine systems can be divided into two operational modalities: real-time mode, which requires the patient's data to be retrieved later on, right after the server end is gathered; and storage and forward mode[26]. Key signals are transmitted to the server over a computer network, mobile telephone, public telephone or cable television network. The expert will use a PC for analysing important signals on the server in such model systems. The patient will be placed in a fixed position, such as the home or the medical facility, where a PC is provided for the transmission of this data. The employment of Wired Network connected computers limits the freedom of mobility of doctors and patients[9], [27].

Structural challenges and existing methodology in India

The authentication of these challenges was based on several secondary data sources after the author determined what are the main barriers facing public hospitals in India. Furthermore, the authors' observations, in conjunction with the State Health Systems resource Center, the Government of India Technical Consultation Office of the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, were also relying on during their follow-up visits to various health facilities, in particular Uttarakhand and Uttar Pradesh States[28].

Through the process several of these challenges were profiled, on the basis of data from relevant literacy, in the social, economic and political sources. Following the analysis contained in the review and understanding of the author, remedies have been devised to identify certain of these socio economic and political aspects. The treatments offered are nevertheless capable of allowing changes to the socio economic and political structure of society within the present system[29].

Furthermore, an effort to carefully evaluate the problems in a public hospital does not focus on the study to achieve obvious clarity. Otherwise, the inherently interlinked nature of the various difficulties facing a public hospital in India is usually lost of sight through a partialist approach. We feel that a solution cannot be found that in its scope is strictly limited to one component of the problem at stake, without affecting other elements. This is therefore a thorough review[14].

Government Hospitals Lack Sanitation, Medical Facilities in all major cities

At the government hospitals throughout few countries, the lack of essential medical amenities and bad sanitary conditions have added to the difficulties of suffering patients, as a factual inspection operation by ANI in these hospitals. There is a lack of sanitation and cleanliness in the Uttar Pradesh, Moradabad District Hospital and the Kanpur Ursula Hospital, causing great concern to patients and workers[30][31].

There are no essential health facilities such as ambulances, stretchers and wheelchair in the hospital. Participants must travel to the hospital ward or parking area independently. Patients wait for hours to receive effective care because of the shortage of doctors.

Patients, on the other hand, have to sleep on the damp floors due to the water leak from the toilets in Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose District Hospital in Gorakhpur, and officials don't even monitor these[32].

The Guru Nanak Government Hospital in Amritsar has low facilities and hygienic conditions in Punjab with piles of waste and filth. Because of broken beds and stretchers, patients sit in the ward. Assistants spread throughout the hospital, creating a terrible environment for the patients suffering[7], [15].

In Ranchi's hospitals, a wide range of advisories was given to ensure cleanliness to prepare for any eventuality, as well as reporting any suspected fever cases promptly on Wednesday, amidst Acute Encephalitis Syndrome (AES) outbreaks. In Bihar's Muzaffarpur area, as many as 112 children have been killed. The lack of medical care and inadequate healthcare facilities is causing patients in Bowring and Lady Curzon Hospital in Bangalore[33].

The following are the major problems of health services in India:

1. Neglect of Rural Population:

Nevertheless, India's health facilities suffer from neglect of rural populations. The hospital is largely urban. Although there are no PHC and rural hospitals, urban distortions remain clear. 31.5 percent of hospitals and 16 percent of hospital beds live in rural areas in 75 percent of the overall population, according to health figures. In addition, doctors are not ready to serve in remote regions. Instead of establishing a paramedics based emergency health system, the peripherals are enhanced (like doctors in China). To make this really hefty, India has invented a trusted doctor.

2. Emphasis on Culture Method:

The health system in India depends almost on imported Western models. It has no roots in the culture and culture of people. It is mostly a hospital service in urban areas. This is to the detriment of giving adequate primary health care to everyone. Otherwise, measures in the field of prevention, motivation, reconstruction and public health were mainly overlooked.

3. Inadequate structure for Health:

According to the 2002 National Health Policy, the government's participation in the healthcare industry is just 0.9 percent of GDP. It isn't sufficient. Public healthcare to 24.9 per cent in China and 45.4 and 44.1 in Sri Lanka and the US, public expenditure in India is 17.3 per cent. Health costs are comparable in China. This is the main reason for the low health standards in the country.

4. Social Inequality:

The rise of health facilities in India was marked by a major imbalance. Country is served in rural, hilly and remote locations, and health facilities in major cities and cities are being created. The SC/ST and the impoverished are far from contemporary healthcare.

The table shows social inequality in provision of health in India.

S. No.	Indicator	All India	SC	ST	Other Disadvantage	Others
1.	Percentage Children Underweight	46.5	53.5	55.9	47.3	41.1
2	Under 5 Mortality Rate	94.9	119.3	126.6	103.1	82.6
3.	Infant Mortality rate(/1000)	70	83	84.2	76	61.8

5. Shortage of Medical Personnel:

In India, there was a large imbalance in the expansion of health facilities. The country is served in rural, hilly and distant places, while health facilities are developed in major cities and towns. The SC/ST and the impoverished are far from contemporary healthcare.

6. Medical Research:

Medical research needs to be concentrated in the country on medicines and tropical disease vaccines which foreign pharmaceutical companies generally avoid due to their limited revenue potential. To encourage medical research in this direction, the National Health Policy 2002 proposes allocating greater cash.

7. Costly Health Service:

In India in particular, allopathic medical services are exceedingly expensive. The regular person has been hit hard. Prices have soared for certain critical pharmaceutical goods. Therefore it should be given greater significance to the diverse medical avenues. The Ayurveda, Unani and Homeopathy systems are cheaper and more suitable for the general person. The health system has a number of concerns. These issues can be solved by effective planning and allocating additional finances.

Second wave of Covid-19 in India

After killing at least 1.76 lakh lives in the last two months, the Covid curve is finally falling into a zone where the disease, experts think, could be handled by current health infrastructure.

On April 4, India's daily Covid case count surpassed 1 lakh for the first time, kicking off the pandemic's most explosive phase, during which the daily count of new infections peaked at 4.14 lakh on May 6. After killing at least 1.76 lakh lives in the two months after that milestone, the Covid curve is finally falling into a zone where the sickness, specialists say, may be handled by existing health infrastructure. The number of active cases in the country is less than half of

what it was at its height; case counts have begun to drop in nearly every state; and the weekly positive rate has dipped below overall positivity for the first time in more than two months.

Figure 1: Number of New Cases in India During the Pandemic [16]

The biggest consolation is that the daily death toll is beginning to decline. Every day, less than 3,000 people die, compared to a high of almost 4,400 just ten days earlier. The worst may be behind us, but the second wave is yet to arrive. The daily case count, at least 1.22 lakh on Wednesday, is still much higher than the top of the first wave, which peaked at 97,894 on September 16 last year. The number of active cases and the daily death toll are both increasing. And, with the exception of Assam, most North-Eastern states are still seeing a boom.

Figure 2: Vaccination Doses given to states

Figure 3: Vaccination Does given Vs. Vaccination Done

State-sanctioned curfews have undoubtedly aided the situation. However, even if the lockdowns had not occurred, the peak would have occurred around the same time, in the first or second week of May. The only difference is that the peak would have been far greater than the 4.14 lakh recorded. The pandemic's course is roughly in accordance with what our computer model has predicted, so we can state with good certainty that the second wave will be ended by the end of this month assuming nothing unexpected happens. We'd be in the exact spot we'd been before everything started.

Figure 4: Number Death in India due to Pandemic

State-sanctioned curfews have undoubtedly aided the situation. However, even if the lockdowns had not occurred, the peak would have occurred around the same time, in the first or second week of May. The only difference is that the peak would have been far greater than the 4.14 lakh recorded. The pandemic's course is roughly in accordance with what our computer model has predicted, so we can state with good certainty that the second wave will be ended by the end of this month assuming nothing unexpected happens. We'd be in the exact spot we'd been before everything started. Since the beginning of the epidemic last year, over 70 crore individuals in India have been infected (25 times the current case count of 2.8 crore). Even a modest estimate puts the figure at 40 crore people, or around one-third of India's population.

The strength of following waves of infection would be determined by this number. The number of persons who have been vaccinated is another important element. Until present, almost 22 crore Indians have got at least one dosage of the vaccination. Those who have been infected and those who have got the vaccination would have overlap. Even yet, it is estimated that close to 50 crore individuals in India have obtained some level of protection to the virus, either through natural infection or vaccination.

Wake-Up Call

The Indian public-health system is under-funded in a report published by the Confederation of Indian Industry (CII), which calls for Covid19 pandemics to be a "wake-up call" for Indian healthcare.

In the research titled: Improving healthcare, published on Monday, the Primary Health Center (PHC) members are generally overburdened by insufficient staff in many countries, but for the epidemic control Covid-19, all public health efforts include testing, early diagnosis of cases, and preventative measures. The research highlights a further worsening of the situation as primary health care centres have been overburdened already via the crisis and a major resource constraint by the lack of basic supplies and equipment and the lack of competent medical and para-medical staff in long-hour taskings. The medical and parathirmaking personnel is a doctor, nurses, siblings, auxiliary nursing siblings, ASHAs and staff from Anganwadi.

"The Covid-19 outbreak has shown weaknesses in the system and our underinvestment in public health infrastructure overall. Dr RandeepGuleria, Director of the All India Institute of Medical Science (AIIMS), New Delhi and CII Public Health Council Chairman explained that we need a coordinated strategy to tackle the challenges that lie before us. He spoke at a CII virtual event under the title "Healthcare Ecosystem Redefinition," in association with the Ministry and Family Welfare and the Ayush Ministry. "Our rural infrastructure quality is low, and our aim must be to

strengthen rural health infrastructure via state and nursing homes, as well as to strengthen the workforce and to strengthen our regional capacities," added Guleria.

The Indian Public Health system is a multilayered structure with a population of around 3,000-5,000 in around five villages at the base of the pyramid. The primary base of PHCs is usually six sub-centres, operating as referral units. PHC works as a central and flowing centre, followed by sub-district and district hospitals, into community health care (CHCs). At the top are medical universities and elite institutes of research such as the All India Medical Sciences Institute.

"Primary health care improvement challenges include limited resources for equipment, medicines and supplies of vaccines, poor workforce, unable to manage the caseload, clean bathrooms and overall health facilities," said the report.

While the SOPs and guidance are in place, challenges in nations with a small working population that can only be enhanced via effective collaboration in public-private partnership types continue to strengthen test procedures. The resilience of the leading staff must be reinforced over years, to build response techniques not just for this epidemic but also for future health emergencies. In this analysis, it was emphasised that, in 2020–21, the percentage allocated to basic and secondary health care by the Union health mission fell to 49%, from 56% in 2018–19; however, the percentage supplied for higher healthcare insurance schemes has more than doubled, from 4% to 9% during the same period. In support of PHC, the declining trend must be rapidly rectified and extended to at least 70% of all health expenditures.

References :

- [1] J. G. Júnior, J. P. de Sales, M. M. Moreira, W. R. Pinheiro, C. K. T. Lima, and M. L. R. Neto, "A crisis within the crisis: The mental health situation of refugees in the world during the 2019 coronavirus (2019-nCoV) outbreak," *Psychiatry Res.*, vol. 288, p. 113000, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113000>.
- [2] V. K. Manupati, M. Ramkumar, V. Baba, and A. Agarwal, "Selection of the best healthcare waste disposal techniques during and post COVID-19 pandemic era," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 281, p. 125175, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125175>.
- [3] L. Casini and M. Rocchetti, "A Cross-Regional Analysis of the COVID-19 Spread during the 2020 Italian Vacation Period: Results from Three Computational Models Are Compared," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 24, 2020, doi: 10.3390/s20247319.
- [4] E. Gaetani, L. Aniello, R. Baldoni, F. Lombardi, A. Margheri, and V. Sassone, "Blockchain-based database to ensure data integrity in cloud computing environments," Jan. 2017, [Online]. Available: <https://eprints.soton.ac.uk/411996/>.
- [5] S. K. Chowdhary, A. Yadav, and N. Garg, "Cloud computing: Future prospect for e-health," in *2011 3rd International Conference on Electronics Computer Technology*, 2011, vol. 3, pp. 297–299.
- [6] K. P. Iyengar, V. K. Jain, A. Vaish, R. Vaishya, L. Maini, and H. Lal, "Post COVID-19: Planning strategies to resume orthopaedic surgery –challenges and considerations," *J. Clin. Orthop. Trauma*, vol. 11, pp. S291–S295, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcot.2020.04.028>.
- [7] M. Kaliszewski, M. Włodarski, J. Młyńczak, and K. Koczyński, "Comparison of Low-Cost Particulate Matter Sensors for Indoor Air Monitoring during COVID-19 Lockdown," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 24, 2020, doi: 10.3390/s20247290.
- [8] M. Aldwairi and A. Alwahedi, "Detecting Fake News in Social Media Networks," *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, vol. 141, pp. 215–222, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2018.10.171>.
- [9] D. Milea, S. Azmi, P. Reginald, P. Verpillat, and C. Francois, "A review of accessibility of

- administrative healthcare databases in the Asia-Pacific region,” *J. Mark. Access & Heal. Policy*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 28076, 2015, doi: 10.3402/jmahp.v3.28076.
- [10] A. S. Bali and M. Ramesh, “Governing healthcare in India: a policy capacity perspective,” *Int. Rev. Adm. Sci.*, vol. 87, no. 2, pp. 275–293, 2021, doi: 10.1177/00208523211001499.
- [11] A. Kumar and S. K. Mohanty, “Intra-urban Differentials in the Utilization of Reproductive Healthcare in India, 1992–2006,” *J. Urban Heal.*, vol. 88, no. 2, pp. 311–328, 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11524-010-9532-7.
- [12] S. K. Rout, K. S. Sahu, and S. Mahapatra, “Utilization of health care services in public and private healthcare in India: Causes and determinants,” *Int. J. Healthc. Manag.*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 509–516, 2021, doi: 10.1080/20479700.2019.1665882.
- [13] S. P. Padala, A. M. Jendro, and L. C. Orr, “Facetime to reduce behavioral problems in a nursing home resident with Alzheimer’s dementia during COVID-19,” *Psychiatry Res.*, vol. 288, p. 113028, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113028>.
- [14] S. Rudrappa, D. V. Agarkhed, and S. S. Vaidya, “Healthcare Systems: India,” in *Quality Spine Care: Healthcare Systems, Quality Reporting, and Risk Adjustment*, J. Ratliff, T. J. Albert, J. Cheng, and J. Knightly, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2019, pp. 211–224.
- [15] S. K. Mishra, S. D. Gupta, and J. Kaur, “Telemedicine in India: Initiatives and vision,” in *2007 9th International Conference on e-Health Networking, Application and Services*, 2007, pp. 81–83.
- [16] M. Chakraborty and K. M. A. Khan, “A case study on the importance of Human Resource Information System in the Healthcare sector of a corporate Hospital in India,” in *2019 International Conference on Digitization (ICD)*, 2019, pp. 115–117, doi: 10.1109/ICD47981.2019.9105864.
- [17] N. Sharma, A. Anand, and A. Husain, “CLOUD BASED HEALTHCARE SERVICES FOR TELEMEDICINE PRACTICES USING INTERNET OF THINGS,” vol. 7, no. 14, pp. 2605–2611, 2020.
- [18] C. O. Rolim, F. L. Koch, C. B. Westphall, J. Werner, A. Fracalossi, and G. S. Salvador, “A Cloud Computing Solution for Patient’s Data Collection in Health Care Institutions,” in *2010 Second International Conference on eHealth, Telemedicine, and Social Medicine*, 2010, pp. 95–99.
- [19] Wang Ping, Wang Jin-gang, Shi Xiao-bo, and He Wei, “The Research of Telemedicine System Based on Embedded Computer,” in *2005 IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology 27th Annual Conference*, 2005, pp. 114–117.
- [20] A. Jebrane, N. Meddah, A. Toumanari, and M. Bousseta, “New Real Time Cloud Telemedicine Using Digital Signature Algorithm on Elliptic Curves,” in *Advanced Information Technology, Services and Systems*, 2018, pp. 324–332.
- [21] C. Kugean, S. M. Krishnan, O. Chutatape, S. Swaminathan, N. Srinivasan, and P. Wang, “Design of a mobile telemedicine system with wireless LAN,” in *Asia-Pacific Conference on Circuits and Systems*, 2002, vol. 1, pp. 313–316 vol.1.
- [22] M. Krzyśko, W. Wołyński, M. Szymkowiak, and A. Wojtyła, “A Spatio-Temporal Analysis of the Health Situation in Poland Based on Functional Discriminant Coordinates,” *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, vol. 18, no. 3, 2021, doi: 10.3390/ijerph18031109.
- [23] R. Das *et al.*, “Role of Withaferin A and Its Derivatives in the Management of Alzheimer’s Disease: Recent Trends and Future Perspectives,” *Molecules*, vol. 26, no. 12, 2021, doi: 10.3390/molecules26123696.
- [24] P. Matlani and N. D. Londhe, “A cloud computing based telemedicine service,” in *2013 IEEE Point-of-Care Healthcare Technologies (PHT)*, 2013, pp. 326–330.
- [25] F. J. Vivas Fernández *et al.*, “ResUHUrge: A Low Cost and Fully Functional Ventilator Indicated for Application in COVID-19 Patients,” *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 23, 2020, doi: 10.3390/s20236774.
- [26] C. C. Yang and L. Jiang, “Enriching User Experience in Online Health Communities Through Thread Recommendations and Heterogeneous Information Network Mining,” *IEEE Trans.*

- Comput. Soc. Syst.*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 1049–1060, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TCSS.2018.2879044.
- [27] A. F. Silva and M. Tavakoli, “Domiciliary Hospitalization through Wearable Biomonitoring Patches: Recent Advances, Technical Challenges, and the Relation to Covid-19,” *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 23, 2020, doi: 10.3390/s20236835.
- [28] D. Palasamudram and S. Avinash, “ICT Solution for Managing Electronic Health Record in India,” in *2012 Third International Conference on Services in Emerging Markets*, 2012, pp. 65–74, doi: 10.1109/ICSEM.2012.17.
- [29] A. R. Basu, D. Kumar, S. Goel, B. Gandhi, and P. Tripathi, “Measuring the Lockdown Effectiveness in Arresting Covid-19 in India,” in *2020 IEEE Recent Advances in Intelligent Computational Systems (RAICS)*, 2020, pp. 165–169, doi: 10.1109/RAICS51191.2020.9332504.
- [30] A. Ghosh, S. Nundy, and T. K. Mallick, “How India is dealing with COVID-19 pandemic,” *Sensors Int.*, vol. 1, p. 100021, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sintl.2020.100021>.
- [31] S. Ghosh, A. K. Das, and A. Yadav, “Optimum Testing Strategy for COVID-19 and Its Effect on Health Expenditure in India: An Experience of the Initial 155 Days of the Pandemic,” *Indian Econ. J.*, vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 383–395, 2020, doi: 10.1177/0019466220981822.
- [32] E. Silfwerbrand, S. Verma, C. Sjökvist, C. Stålsby Lundborg, and M. Sharma, “Diagnose-Specific Antibiotic Prescribing Patterns at Otorhinolaryngology Inpatient Departments of Two Private Sector Healthcare Facilities in Central India: A Five-Year Observational Study,” *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, vol. 16, no. 21, 2019, doi: 10.3390/ijerph16214074.
- [33] S. Capolongo, “A New Challenge in Healthcare for India,” in *Healthcare Facilities in Emerging Countries: The Challenge for India*, S. Capolongo, M. Gola, and A. Rebecchi, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018, pp. 1–11.